

by the computational method of Rossotti and Rossotti⁶. Maximum $\bar{n}$ values obtained in the present experiments was 2.5 which also supports our assumption of 1 : 3 complex formation. Mean log K values are presented in Table 1. The overall stability constants log β_3 for the rare earth-cinnamohydroxamate complexes were not comparable to

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANT VALUES OF LANTHANIDE-CINNAMOHYDROXAMATE COMPLEXES IN DIOXANF-WATER SOLVENT

Temp. = $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$, $\mu = 0.1 M$
 $pK^HCHA = 6.93$

Metal ion	$1/r(A^{0-1})$	log K_1	log K_2	log K_3	log β_3
La ^{III}	0.942	4.04	3.92	2.98	10.91
Nd ^{III}	1.005	4.53	4.04	3.24	10.81
Sm ^{III}	1.037	4.84	4.26	3.41	12.51

those of NBPHA³ (in the same solvent mixture) or salicylhydroxamic acid⁹ (in acetone-water solvent). In fact the log β_3 values of the lanthanide-NBPHA (≈ 22) and salicylhydroxamate complexes (≈ 19) were much higher than those of CHA complexes (≈ 11). Solid complexes of La^{III}, Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} with CHA have been prepared and analysed. The composition of these complexes were found to be LnL₃·xH₂O (x=2 for La^{III} and 1 for Nd^{III} and Sm^{III}). The analytical data are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA OF HYDRATED LANTHANIDE-CINNAMOHYDROXAMATE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found (Calcd.)		
		M	N	C
La(C ₉ H ₈ NO ₃) ₃ ·2H ₂ O	White	21.00 (21.01)	6.25 (6.35)	48.98 (49.02)
Nd(C ₉ H ₈ NO ₃) ₃ ·H ₂ O	Pale pink	21.70 (21.85)	6.45 (6.51)	50.00 (50.25)
Sm(C ₉ H ₈ NO ₃) ₃	White	22.95 (22.98)	6.40 (6.41)	49.55 (49.50)

The ir spectra of the solid complexes showed broad bands (above 3 000 cm⁻¹), which could be ascribed to the presence of either coordinated or lattice water¹⁰. The $\nu_{C=O}$ of CHA (1 665 cm⁻¹) has been found to shift to 1 640 cm⁻¹ in its sodium salt, whereas, for the lanthanide complexes a further shift towards lower frequencies (1 632 for La^{III}, 1 635 for Nd^{III} and 1 632 cm⁻¹ for Sm^{III} complexes) were observed. The strong ν_{ON} (at 1 350 cm⁻¹) and ν_{NO} (at 976 cm⁻¹) bands of the free ligand were shifted to 1 370 and 960 cm⁻¹, respectively in the complexes. Thus, the lanthanide ions were probably attached to two coordination sites (C=O and NHO⁻) of the cinnamohydroxamate ion.

Acknowledgement

Thanks of the authors are due to Dr. M. Chaudhury of the I.A.C.S, Calcutta, for his help during this work.

References

1. S. P. SINHA, "Complexes of the Rare Earths", Pergamon Press, London, 1966.
2. S. K. BRAHMA and A. K. CHAKRABURTTY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 942.
3. J. THIELE and R. H. PICKARD, *Ann. Chem.*, 1899, **194**, 309.
4. S. K. BRAHMA and A. K. CHAKRABURTTY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 1723.
5. K. NAG and M. CHAUDHURY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, **15**, 921.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "A Textbook of Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd ed., Longmans, London, p. 177.
7. L. G. VAN UITFERT and C. G. HASS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 451.
8. F. J. C. ROSSOTTI and E. ROSSOTTI, "The Determination of Stability Constants", McGraw-Hill, London, 1961, p. 88.
9. N. K. DUTTA and T. SESHADRI, *Talanta*, 1970, **17**, 168.
10. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 3rd ed., Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1978, p. 227.

**Rare Earths Complexes of some Amino Acids
A Polarographic Study**

FARID KHAN*

Department of Chemistry, Doctor Harisingh Gour
Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar-470 003

Manuscript received 29 November 1984, revised 30 September 1985, accepted 17 January 1986

AMINO acids have been used as complexing reagents with various metal ions¹⁻³. Tewari and Shrivastava⁶ reported the stability constants of La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} and Y^{III} complexes with L-asparagine and L-glutamine by potentiometric technique. The present paper is continuation of our previous work⁷⁻⁹ and was undertaken with the view to determine the formation constants and thermodynamic parameters of Ce^{III} complexes with L-alanine, L-glutamine and L-asparagine on a dropping mercury electrode.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A. R. grade. The solution of L-alanine (Eastman & Kodak), L-glutamine (B. D. H., England) and L-asparagine (E. Merck) were prepared in double distilled water and their purity was checked by chromatographic method¹⁰. The metal solution was prepared by dissolving weighted quantity of CeCl₃·6H₂O (Fluka, A G.) in distilled water and was standardised with EDTA¹¹. The overall concentration of Ce^{III}, potassium chloride and gelatin in the test electrolytic solution was 1.0 mM, 1.0 M and 0.01%, respectively. The concentration of ligand was varied from 1.0 to 10.0 mM in each case. For the adjustment of ionic strength (μ) at 1.0 M, potassium chloride was used. Sodium hydroxide and hydro-

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF 1 : 1 COMPLEXES OF Ce^{III} $\mu = 1.00 M KCl$

Ligands	log K at temp. (°C)			ΔH k cal mol ⁻¹ at temp. (difference of 10°)		ΔG k cal mol ⁻¹ at temp. (°C)			ΔS cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹ at temp. (°C)		
	25	35	45	(35-25)	(45-35)	25	35	45	25	33	45
	L-Alanine	6.10	5.60	5.00	-21.14	40.28	-8.37	-7.94	-7.32	-42.83	-42.85
L-Glutamine	3.72	3.15	2.65	-24.09	-37.95	-5.11	-4.47	-3.88	-63.70	-63.71	-107.14
L-Asparagine	3.52	3.60	-2.60	-21.99	-39.097	-4.83	-4.25	-3.80	-57.58	-57.60	-110.99

chloric acid were used to maintain pH of the test solution at 2.70 ± 0.02 .

pH measurements were made on a Elico LI-120 digital pH meter. Polarograms were recorded on an automatic pen recording polarograph (C. I. C., India). The capillary used had an 'm' value 2.18 mg s^{-1} and drop time 3.0 s at 43.0 cm effective height of mercury. Nitrogen gas was passed to remove dissolved oxygen from the solution before recording the polarograms. Measurements were made at 25, 35 and 45°.

Results and Discussion

A well defined three electron reversible reduction wave of Ce^{III} has been reported^{12,13} at pH 2.70 ± 0.02 in 1.0 M potassium chloride with 0.01% gelatin used as a maximum suppressor. The slopes of linear plots of $\log i/(i_a - i)$ vs $E_{a,e}$ were of the order of $21 \pm 1 \text{ mV}$ for Ce^{III} and its complexes with all the three ligands indicating reversibility of the electrode process. The straight line plots of j_a vs $\sqrt{h}$ for metal ion and its complexes showed the diffusion-controlled nature of the waves. The reduction potential of Ce^{III} was -1.85 V against S.C.E. at pH 2.70 ± 0.02 .

The half-wave potential shifted to more negative value on increasing the concentration of ligand. The method of Lingane¹⁴ was used to determine composition and stability constants. Thermodynamic parameters were calculated from the well known thermodynamic relations¹⁵ and tabulated in Table 1.

The order of stability constants of Ce^{III} complexes with respect to ligands was found L-asparagine < L-glutamine < L-alanine and decrease with the increase of temperature.

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to Head of the Department of Chemistry, for facilities.

References

1. E. M. ROGOZINA and T. M. PONIKAROVA, *Zh. Obsch. Khim.*, 1970, 40, 2357.
2. E. M. ROGOZINA and T. M. PONIKAROVA, *Zh. Obsch. Khim.*, 1968, 38, 1957.
3. S. D. MAKHIJANI and S. P. SANGAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 670.
4. B. S. SEKHON and S. L. CHOPRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, 12, 1322.

5. V. E. PLYUSHCHEV, G. V. NADEZHINA, G. S. LOSEVA, V. V. MELLNIKOVA and T. S. PARFEROVA, *Izv. Vyssh. Uchebn. Zaved. Khim. Tekhnol.*, 1975, 18, 1029.
6. R. C. TEWARI and M. N. SHRIVASTAVA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, 35, 3044.
7. F. KHAN and A. V. MAHAJANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 996.
8. F. KHAN and A. V. MAHAJANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 60, 296.
9. F. KHAN, V. K. CHITALE and A. V. MAHAJANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, 61, 165.
10. A. A. KHAN and W. U. MALIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 10, 566.
11. F. J. WELCHER, "The Analytical Uses of Ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid", Van Nostrand, New York, 1957, pp. 174, 181.
12. L. MEITES, "Polarographic Technique", Interscience, New York, 1965, p. 628.
13. K. S. PITRE and V. K. CHITALE, "Proceedings of the Convention of Chemists: Abstract", 1980, Indian Chemical Society, Calcutta, Anal. 11.
14. J. J. LINGANE, *Chem. Rev.*, 1941, 29, 1.
15. K. B. YATSIMIRSKII and V. P. VASIL'EV, "Instability Constants of Complex Compounds", Pergamon, London, 1960, p. 60.

Physicochemical Studies of Complex Formation of Cyclopentane Tetracarboxylic Acid with Alkaline Earth Metals

A. K. MISRA*

Central Road Research Institute, New Delhi-110 020
and

K. SRINIVASULU

School of Studies in Chemistry, Vikram University, Ujjain

Manuscript received 20 May 1985, revised 16 September 1985,
accepted 17 January 1986

CIS, cis, cis, cis-1,2,3,4-Cyclopentanetetracarboxylic acid (CPTA) and its different compounds were used for various purposes, such as in resins and rubber preparation¹, for plasticisers², and for surface treatment of metals and plasters³. So far, a systematic study of its complexes seems to be lacking although as a quadridentate ligand it has been of great interest in coordination chemistry. The present investigation deals with the determination of the formation constants of the all *cis*-